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Building Global Health Solidarity in a Permacrisis: Legal Impacts of a Pandemic Treaty

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ABSTRACT

COVID-19 has revealed the urgent need for global solidarity in an era of interconnected crises (permacrisis). The World Health Organization (WHO) aims to improve pandemic prevention, preparedness and response through a ‘convention, agreement or another international instrument under the constitution of WHO’ (‘pandemic treaty’). This study analyses shortcomings in global health solidarity during COVID-19, investigates legal impacts of the pandemic treaty and navigates the arguments for and against a pandemic treaty. The treaty’s potential legal implications for human rights, intellectual property law, tort law, global health law, competition law and public procurement are examined, as well as some challenges to its implementation. The treaty’s success depends on overcoming differences and learning from global failure in order to prepare better for the next pandemic. The pandemic treaty must ensure equity, transparency, accountability and human rights while facilitating access to vaccines and other pandemic-related products, especially for low- and middle-income countries.

INTRODUCTION

The term ‘crisis’ was frequently used from 11 March 2020, when the WHO announced that COVID-19 was a pandemic,¹ to May 2023, when the WHO

¹ WHO, *Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) situation report–51* (Geneva, 2020), available at: https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/coronaviruse/situation-reports/20200311-sitrep-51-covid-19.pdf?sfvrsn=1ba62e57_10 (20 September 2023).

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declared that COVID-19 was no longer a ‘public health emergency of international concern’.² ‘Permacrisis’, however, describes a higher crisis level. The *Cambridge Dictionary* defines it as ‘a long period of great difficulty, confusion, or suffering that seems to have no end’. A permacrisis is when ‘catastrophic events’ such as wars, epidemics, pandemics, humanitarian crises, food insecurity, climate change and widespread regional conflicts occur more frequently and intensely.³

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the shortcomings of national policies and the fragility of health systems became more evident than ever. The pandemic highlighted an urgent need for global solidarity, cooperation and prompt response.⁴ It led to the starting of an initiative by the WHO to draft a ‘treaty,⁵ convention, agreement or other international instrument’ for combating future health crises.⁶ This study examines the legal impacts and challenges of establishing a pandemic treaty, in light of the global health solidarity failures during COVID-19. According to the preamble of the pandemic treaty’s (bureau) draft, this international initiative should respond to the ‘catastrophic failure of the international community in showing solidarity and equity to coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic’.⁷

There are different views in the literature on the potential of a pandemic treaty to promote global solidarity in future health crises. Perehudoff et al. highlight the potential of a pandemic treaty to address the underlying inequities caused by a global health crisis and establish a more effective solidarity-based framework for the global management of medical countermeasures. Their recommendations focus on intellectual property (IP) and know-how sharing, technology transfer, enhancing research and development financing and increasing

² WHO, ‘Statement on the fifteenth meeting of the IHR (2005) Emergency Committee on the COVID-19 pandemic’, available at: [https://www.who.int/news/item/05-05-2023-statement-on-the-fifteenth-meeting-of-the-international-health-regulations-\(2005\)-emergency-committee-regarding-the-coronavirus-disease-\(covid-19\)-pandemic](https://www.who.int/news/item/05-05-2023-statement-on-the-fifteenth-meeting-of-the-international-health-regulations-(2005)-emergency-committee-regarding-the-coronavirus-disease-(covid-19)-pandemic) (20 September 2023).

³ Josh Glancy, ‘Will the permacrisis ever end?’, *Sunday Times*, 26 February 2022. Some authors used the words ‘polycrisis’ and ‘metacrisis’. For an explanation of each of these terms, see Bendell Jem, ‘Replacing sustainable development: potential frameworks for international cooperation in an era of increasing crises and disasters’, *Sustainability* 14 (2022), 8185.

⁴ Susi Geiger and Nicole Gross, ‘Tech sharing, not tech hoarding: Covid-19, global solidarity, and the failed responsibility of the pharmaceutical industry’, *Organization* (31 January 2023), 13505084221145666.

⁵ WHO aims to enhance pandemic prevention, preparedness and response through a ‘convention, agreement, or another international instrument under the Constitution of WHO’. The name and legal nature of this instrument are still unclear. Pandemic preparedness treaty, pandemic accord and WHO CA+ are alternative names for the pandemic treaty; in this paper, I utilise the term ‘pandemic treaty’ for consistency.

⁶ WHO, ‘World Health Assembly agrees to launch process to develop historic global accord on pandemic prevention, preparedness and response’, available at: <https://www.who.int/news/item/01-12-2021-world-health-assembly-agrees-to-launch-process-to-develop-historic-global-accord-on-pandemic-prevention-preparedness-and-response> (20 September 2023).

⁷ WHO, Drafting Group of the Intergovernmental Negotiating Body to Draft and Negotiate a WHO Convention, Agreement or Other International Instrument on Pandemic Prevention, Preparedness and Response, ‘Draft Bureau’s text of the WHO CA+: WHO convention, agreement or other international instrument on pandemic prevention, preparedness and response’ (‘WHO CA+’), 2 June 2023, available at: https://apps.who.int/gb/inb/pdf_files/inb5/A_INB5_6-en.pdf (21 September 2023).

the effectiveness of regulatory standards and procedures for pandemic-related products.⁸

Lee and Ming argue that a pandemic response framework must be built on universal solidarity through modifying International Health Regulations (IHR)⁹ or creating a new treaty.¹⁰ Wenham et al. express scepticism about the effectiveness of a pandemic treaty, claiming that it would not address the challenges of global cooperation in global health.¹¹

The article is structured as follows. The next section examines global health solidarity's shortcomings during the COVID-19 pandemic. The following section looks at the pandemic treaty as a solution to enhance this solidarity and navigates the arguments for and against it. The paper's final section reviews the legal impacts of the treaty on human rights, IP law, tort law, global health law, competition law and public procurement and explores some concerns related to the implementation of the pandemic treaty.

GLOBAL HEALTH SOLIDARITY'S SHORTCOMINGS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

The political, economic, social, legal and psychological impacts of COVID-19 on our lives have been considerable.¹² During the pandemic, we faced several challenges at the global level, such as pressure on health systems; vaccine development, production and distribution; disrupted supply chains; pandemic profiteering;¹³ pandemic infodemic;¹⁴ vaccine nationalism;¹⁵ human rights violations;¹⁶ and more

⁸ Katrina Pehudoff, Ellen 't Hoen, Katerini Mara, Thiru Balasubramaniam, Frederick Abbott, Brook Baker, et al., 'A pandemic treaty for equitable global access to medical countermeasures: seven recommendations for sharing intellectual property, know-how and technology', *BMJ Global Health* 7 (7) (2022), e009709.

⁹ The International Health Regulations (2005) are established 'to prevent, protect against, control and provide a public health response to the international spread of disease in ways that are commensurate with and restricted to public health risks, and which avoid unnecessary interference with international traffic and trade'.

¹⁰ Po-Han Lee and Ming-Jui Yeh, 'From security to solidarity: the normative foundation of a global pandemic treaty', *Journal of Global Health* 12 (2022), 1–3.

¹¹ Clare Wenham, Mark Eccleston-Turner and Maike Voss, 'The futility of the pandemic treaty: caught between globalism and statism', *International Affairs* 98 (3) (2022), 837–52.

¹² See, for example, Orestis Delardas, Konstantinos S. Kechagias, Pantelis N. Pontikos and Panagiotis Giannos, 'Socio-economic impacts and challenges of the coronavirus pandemic (COVID-19): an updated review', *Sustainability* 14 (15) (2022), 9699–712.

¹³ See, for example, Kaushik Bhattacharya and Neela Bhattacharya, 'Pandemic profiteering during the second wave of Covid-19', *Indian Journal of Medical Ethics* 7 (2) (2022), 166–7; Julia Kollewe, 'Pfizer accused of pandemic profiteering as profits double', *The Guardian*, 8 February 2022.

¹⁴ 'Infodemic' is defined in the Pandemic Treaty Draft (June 2023) as 'too much information including false or misleading information in the digital and physical environment during a disease outbreak'. See Parth Patwa, Shivam Sharma, Srinivas Pykl, Vineeth Guptha, Gitanjali Kumari, Md Shad Akhtar, Asif Ekbal, et al., 'Fighting an infodemic: Covid-19 fake news dataset', Combating Online Hostile Posts in Regional Languages during Emergency Situation: First International Workshop, CONSTRAINT 2021, Revised Selected Papers 1 (Cham, 2021), 21–9; Mohan P. Patel, Vivek B. Kute, Sanjay K. Agarwal, and on behalf of COVID-19 Working Group of Indian Society of Nephrology, 'Infodemic COVID 19: more pandemic than the virus', *Indian Journal of Nephrology* 30 (3) (2020), 188–91.

¹⁵ See David P. Fidler, 'Vaccine nationalism's politics', *Science* 369 (6505) (2020), 749.

¹⁶ Lawrence O. Gostin, Eric A. Friedman, Sara Hossain, Joia Mukherjee, Saman Zia-Zarifi, Chelsea Clinton, et al. 'Human rights and the COVID-19 pandemic: a retrospective and prospective analysis', *The Lancet* 401 (10371) (2023), 154–68.

significant pressures on vulnerable parts of society.¹⁷ These examples merely provide a glimpse into the broader catastrophic scope of the problem.

As Ho and Dascalu¹⁸ mentioned, global health solidarity emphasises the duty of cooperation and coordination between countries to tackle global health problems. Solidarity as a moral value goes far beyond charity,¹⁹ and COVID-19 proved that merely donating COVID-19 vaccines to lower- and middle-income countries (LMICs) was not enough to combat new variants of the pandemic. Health crises could spread beyond national borders, and sharing resources, technologies,²⁰ data, and responsibility²¹ in promoting health equity²² must be at the heart of global health frameworks.

The inequities in COVID-19 vaccine distribution increased the death toll, especially in the Global South.²³ Some factors contributing to this inequity were the hoarding of vaccines by some high-income countries,²⁴ the excessive pricing of pandemic-related products²⁵ and the lack of effectiveness of some international programmes, such as COVAX²⁶ and ACT-Accelerator.²⁷ Vaccine nationalism, limited global manufacturing and distribution capacity, IP rights barriers, and lack of infrastructure, incentive or cooperation for technology transfer and sharing know-how with LMICs were other reasons for the ineffectiveness of solidarity-based initiatives during the COVID-19 pandemic.

¹⁷ Vera Lúcia Raposo and Teresa Violante, 'Access to health care by migrants with precarious status during a health crisis: some insights from Portugal', *Human Rights Review* 22 (4) (2021), 459–82.

¹⁸ Anita Ho and Iulia Dascalu, 'Relational solidarity and COVID-19: an ethical approach to disrupt the global health disparity pathway', *Global Bioethics* 32 (1) (2021), 34–50.

¹⁹ Peter G.N. West-Oram and Alena Buyx, 'Global health solidarity', *Public Health Ethics* 10 (2) (2017), 212–24.

²⁰ Matthew M. Kavanagh, 'Sharing technology and vaccine doses to address global vaccine inequity and end the COVID-19 pandemic', *Journal of the American Medical Association* 326 (3) (2021), 219–20.

²¹ Melinda C. Mills and David Salisbury, 'The challenges of distributing COVID-19 vaccinations', *eClinical Medicine* 31 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eclinm.2020.100674>.

²² Jamie Keiko Fujioka, Suman Budhwani, Tyla Thomas-Jacques, Kristina De Vera, Priyanka Challa, Kaitlin Fuller, et al., 'Challenges and strategies for promoting health equity in virtual care: protocol for a scoping review of reviews', *JMIR Research Protocols* 9 (12) (2020), e22847.

²³ For a review of some of these inequities in the Global South, see Nelson Aghogho Evaborhene, Echezona Ejike Udokanma, Yusuff Adebayo Adebisi, Chinonso Emmanuel Okorie, Zacharia Kafuko, Hawa Marguerite Conde, et al., 'The Pandemic Treaty, the Pandemic Fund, and the Global Commons: our scepticism', *BMJ Global Health* 8 (2) (2023), e011431.

²⁴ Vittorio Bufacchi and Ellen C. Byrne, 'Is vaccine hoarding a type of violence?', in Gottfried Schweiger (ed.), *The global and social consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic: an ethical and philosophical reflection* (Cham, 2022), 325–7.

²⁵ Excessive pricing was very common during the Covid-19 pandemic, and although many competition authorities relaxed some competition law enforcement, they had strict rules regarding this anti-competitive practice.

²⁶ Gavi (a public–private global health partnership that aims to increase access to immunisation in developing countries), CEP (the Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations) and WHO started the COVAX programme to give all nations, regardless of their income levels, equitable access to Covid-19 vaccines. Available at: <https://www.who.int/initiatives/act-accelerator/covax> (31 May 2023).

²⁷ The ACT-Accelerator, a joint effort of WHO, the European Commission and other partners, has been established as a collaboration framework to expedite development, production and access to Covid-19 tests, treatments and vaccines. Available at: <https://www.who.int/initiatives/act-accelerator> (31 May 2023). COVAX and the ACT-A have been confronted with significant funding shortfalls, which have impeded their ability to achieve their objectives. The funding gaps caused delays in the procurement, distribution and administration of diagnostics, treatments and vaccines.

Vaccine nationalism has played a negative role in vaccine negotiations and allocation politics, with wealthier nations prioritising the future needs of their populations over the current needs of poorer countries in the Global South. It has undermined global health solidarity during the COVID-19 pandemic, leading to vaccine hoarding and limited resources for other countries, potentially prolonging the pandemic and worsening global health disparities.²⁸

In recent years, some EU policies in the health sector were established based on the solidarity principle. The EU's new 'Pharmaceutical Strategy for Europe', the 'EU Vaccine Strategy'²⁹ and some of the Commission's soft laws during the pandemic are examples of solidarity's importance in European policies.³⁰

COVID-19 has highlighted the necessity of cooperation in resolving public health emergencies, particularly regarding the distribution of vaccines³¹ and other pandemic-related products. Vaccines were developed and authorised for emergencies before the COVID-19 pandemic, yet access to these life-saving medications has varied dramatically worldwide. In a global pandemic, with interconnected lives of people, vaccine inequity between high-income countries and LMICs could spread the virus wider and even create new variants of the disease.³²

Although IHR and other international legal frameworks are available for the global response to public health emergencies, they were ineffective in combating the COVID-19 pandemic. Improving the preparedness and resilience of health systems by using lessons from the COVID-19 experience³³ to address the next global health crisis is the primary premise for a new international pandemic treaty.

²⁸ Yiqing Su, Yanyan Li and Yanggui Liu, 'Common demand vs. limited supply—how to serve the global fight against COVID-19 through proper supply of COVID-19 vaccines', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19 (3) (2022), 1339. Shikha Kukreti, Ahmad Rifai, Sriyani Padmalatha, Chung-Ying Lin, Tsung Yu, Wen-Chien Ko, et al. 'Willingness to obtain COVID-19 vaccination in general population: a systematic review and meta-analysis', *Journal of Global Health* 12 (6) (2022), 50–61.

²⁹ 'to secure timely access to vaccines for Member States and their population while leading the global solidarity effort', EU Vaccines Strategy (2020), available at <https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/coronavirus-response/public-health/eu-vaccines-strategy> (20 September 2023).

³⁰ See Anniek de Ruijter, Roel Beetsma, Brian Burgoon, Francesco Nicoli and Frank Vandenbroucke, 'EU solidarity and policy in fighting infectious diseases: state of play, obstacles, citizen preferences and ways forward', CESifo Working Paper No. 8222 (2020). EU soft law refers to non-binding acts adopted by EU institutions. Even though compliance cannot be enforced in the same way as directives or regulations, recommendations, resolutions, guidelines, communications and white papers can align policies across members and encourage best practices to be adopted based on shared principles. See Fabien Terpan, 'Soft law in the European Union—the changing nature of EU law', *European Law Journal* 21 (1) (2015), 68–96.

³¹ Filipovich Aleksa, 'Vaccine diplomacy during the COVID-19 pandemic on the example of the Republic of Serbia', *International Relations* 4 (2021), 15–31.

³² Yang Ye, 'Equitable access to COVID-19 vaccines makes a life-saving difference to all countries' *Nature Human Behaviour* 6 (2) (2022), 207–16.

³³ Mario Coccia, 'Preparedness of countries to face COVID-19 pandemic crisis: strategic positioning and underlying structural factors to support strategies of prevention of pandemic threats', *Environmental Research* 203 (2021), 111678.

A PANDEMIC TREATY: A SOLUTION TO ENHANCE GLOBAL HEALTH SOLIDARITY

The COVID-19 pandemic sparked interest in strengthening global health governance and enhancing readiness and responsiveness to future pandemics, resulting in the emergence of a pandemic treaty. WHO has spearheaded the drafting and negotiating of ‘a convention, agreement or other international instrument’, which is intended to be founded under the provisions of the WHO constitution. In December 2021, the World Health Assembly decided to initiate the process of creating a comprehensive global treaty that will address pandemic prevention, preparedness and response. Establishing an Intergovernmental Negotiating Body (INB) was necessary to draft and negotiate the treaty to accomplish this goal.³⁴ The INB was established and started to work towards the preparedness of an international document.

A preliminary version of the pandemic treaty called the ‘zero draft’ was released in February 2023, a ‘bureau draft’ in June 2023 and a ‘negotiating draft’ in October 2023.³⁵ The contents of these drafts presented a conceptualisation for enhancing pandemic prevention, preparedness and response via global collaboration.³⁶ Negotiations were initiated during the fourth meeting of the INB regarding the global accord. The objective was to utilise the draft as a framework for negotiating an agreement to safeguard the world from the next pandemic, using the lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic. Member states must approve the pandemic treaty during the 2024 World Health Assembly.³⁷

Arguments in defence of a pandemic treaty

Many scholars argued in defence of an international pandemic document and that a pandemic treaty has many benefits that could address the challenges posed by upcoming pandemics. Phelan argued that a pandemic treaty would offer an opportunity to decolonise international law³⁸ and human rights, as Sekalala et al.

³⁴ WHO, ‘World Health Assembly agrees to launch process to develop historic global accord on pandemic prevention, preparedness and response’, available at: <https://www.who.int/news/item/01-12-2021-world-health-assembly-agrees-to-launch-process-to-develop-historic-global-accord-on-pandemic-prevention-preparedness-and-response> (20 September 2023).

³⁵ WHO, ‘Negotiating text of the WHO convention, agreement or other international instrument on pandemic prevention, preparedness and response (WHO Pandemic Agreement) (A/INB/7/x). (30 October 2023)’, available at: <https://www.paho.org/en/documents/proposal-negotiating-text-who-pandemic-agreement-30-october-2023> (30 October 2023).

³⁶ WHO, ‘Countries begin negotiations on global agreement to protect the world from future pandemic emergencies’ available at: <https://www.who.int/news/item/03-03-2023-countries-begin-negotiations-on-global-agreement-to-protect-world-from-future-pandemic-emergencies> (20 September 2023).

³⁷ WHO, ‘Pandemic prevention, preparedness and response accord’, available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/questions-and-answers/item/pandemic-prevention--preparedness-and-response-accord> (20 September 2023).

³⁸ Alexandra L. Phelan, ‘The World Health Organization’s pandemic treaty’, *BMJ* 380 (2023).

mentioned.³⁹ Frieden and Buissonnière conclude that it is a chance to promote global cooperation and coordination in response to health crises.⁴⁰ Nikogosian and Kickbusch argued that ‘a treaty would protect lives, livelihoods, security, and human rights’.⁴¹ Jecker supported this view by stating that ‘in an interconnected world, the fair sharing of vaccines is morally mandatory’.⁴² Moreover, such a treaty would help ‘break the pandemic cycle’.⁴³

According to Diab et al., the COVID-19 pandemic has demonstrated the need for political leadership and global accountability.⁴⁴ As Voss et al. argued, a pandemic treaty might offer a platform for such leadership by establishing a framework for ensuring accountability and effectiveness in addressing future health crises.⁴⁵

Arguments against a pandemic treaty

While there are many arguments for the necessity of a pandemic treaty to address future health crises, there are some against it.

One argument is based on previous experience in global cooperation. It includes concerns regarding the extent to which countries will comply with the provisions of the treaty, especially considering that numerous international and regional agreements are currently in effect but have not been entirely implemented. The COVID-19 experience proved some countries’ lack of commitment to international law. WHO cannot ensure that all countries will fully comply with and enforce all provisions of a pandemic treaty, because of a lack of political will. In the absence of noncompliance penalties and given the voluntary basis of most commitments, the effectiveness of this treaty is not guaranteed.

A sovereignty-based argument is based on the possible implications of a pandemic treaty on national sovereignty and how it could interfere with

³⁹ Sharifa Sekalala, Lisa Forman, Timothy Hodgson, Moses Mulumba, Hadijah Namyalo-Ganafa and Benjamin Mason Meier, ‘Decolonising human rights: how intellectual property laws result in unequal access to the COVID-19 vaccine’, *BMJ Global Health* 6 (7) (2021), e006169.

⁴⁰ Thomas R. Frieden and Marine Buissonnière, ‘Will a global preparedness treaty help or hinder pandemic preparedness?’, *BMJ Global Health* 6 (5) (2021), e006297.

⁴¹ Haik Nikogosian and Ilona Kickbusch, ‘The case for an international pandemic treaty’, *BMJ* 372 (2021), available at: <https://www.bmj.com/content/bmj/372/bmj.n527.full.pdf> (28 October 2023).

⁴² Nancy S. Jecker, ‘Focus: vaccines: achieving global vaccine equity: the case for an international pandemic treaty’, *Yale Journal of Biology and Medicine* 95 (2) (2022), 271–80.

⁴³ Alexandra Phelan and Colin J. Carlson, ‘A treaty to break the pandemic cycle’, *Science* 377 (6605) (2022), 475–7.

⁴⁴ Ahmed Abdelnaby Diab, Abdelmonem Metwally and Mostafa Mohamed, ‘The failure of global leadership and accountability problems during the COVID-19 pandemic’, *Academy of Strategic Management Journal* 20 (3) (2021), https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3854858.

⁴⁵ Maïke Voss, Clare Wenham, Mark Eccleston-Turner and Rithika Sangameshwaran, ‘A new pandemic treaty: what the World Health Organization needs to do next’, *LSE blog* (30 March 2022), available at: <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/covid19/2022/03/30/a-new-pandemic-treaty-what-the-world-health-organization-needs-to-do-next/> (27 October 2023).

national policies to address a health emergency.⁴⁶ The current negotiations in the national parliaments discuss concerns regarding independence and sovereignty.⁴⁷ A human-rights-based argument is that implementing a pandemic treaty may infringe on civil liberties under the pretext of ensuring public health and safety. According to ‘Principles and Guidelines on Human Rights and Public Health Emergencies’ prepared by a group of human rights and public health scholars, ‘transparency’, ‘access to information’, ‘meaningful and effective public participation in decision making process’, ‘accountability’ and ‘access to justice for those harmed by human rights violation and abuses’ are among human rights considerations and duties of states in a health crisis.⁴⁸

COVID-19 had many negative economic impacts worldwide, triggering recessions and increasing poverty⁴⁹ and inequalities,⁵⁰ especially in the Global South. One argument against this treaty is that some restriction-based provisions might significantly impact the LMICs, and they may have less incentive to comply if it hinders their economic progress. Given the different resources, infrastructure and development of WHO member states, a general global treaty might have some provisions only suitable for some countries.⁵¹

Many conspiracy theories and arguments regarding the pandemic treaty are spreading on social media.⁵² These arguments are based on the belief that a pandemic treaty will create a global health dictatorship and replace each country’s constitution.

⁴⁶ For example, see ‘Why the U.S. should oppose the new draft WHO pandemic treaty’, available at: <https://www.heritage.org/global-politics/report/why-the-us-should-oppose-the-new-draft-who-pandemic-treaty> (20 September 2023).

⁴⁷ See, for example, the Pandemic Treaty discussion in the UK parliament: many members of parliament mentioned sovereignty concerns. Available at: <https://hansard.parliament.uk/commons/2023-04-17/debates/12BE683F-A25C-46E5-9FE9-B9C12CCDA9B7/PandemicPreventionPreparednessAndResponseInternationalAgreement> (20 September 2023).

⁴⁸ Roojin Habibi, Luciano Bottini Filho, Judith Bueno de Mesquita, Gian Luca Burci, Luisa Cabal, Thana Cristina de Campos, Danwood Chirwa, et al., ‘The principles and guidelines on human rights and public health emergencies’, University of Groningen Faculty of Law Research Paper No. 14/2023 (2023), 11–12, available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4454622> (27 October 2023).

⁴⁹ Giovanni Valensisi, ‘COVID-19 and global poverty: are LDCs being left behind?’, *European Journal of Development Research* 32 (5) (2020), 1535–57; Mohamed Buheji, Katiane da Costa Cunha, Godfred Beka, Bartola Mavrić, Yuri Leandro do Carmo de Souza, Simone Souza da Costa Silva, et al., ‘The extent of COVID-19 pandemic socio-economic impact on global poverty: a global integrative, multidisciplinary review’, *American Journal of Economics* 10 (4) (2020), 213–24.

⁵⁰ Benjamin Wachtler, Niels Michalski, Enno Nowossadeck, Michaela Diercke, Morten Wahrendorf, Claudia Santos-Hövenner, et al., ‘Socioeconomic inequalities and COVID-19 – a review of the current international literature’, *Journal of Health Monitoring* 5 (Suppl. 7) (2020), 3–17.

⁵¹ See Clare Wenham, Mark Eccleston-Turner and Maïke Voss, ‘The futility of the pandemic treaty: caught between globalism and statism’, *International Affairs* 98 (3) (2022), 837–52.

⁵² For a fact-check of some of these theories, see: Reuters, ‘Fact check – the WHO is not planning to implement a “pandemic treaty” that would strip member states of sovereignty’, available at: <https://www.reuters.com/article/factcheck-who-treaty/fact-check-the-who-is-not-planning-to-implement-a-pandemic-treaty-that-would-strip-member-states-of-sovereignty-idUSL2N2XH0KA> (2 June 2023).

NAVIGATING THE LEGAL IMPACTS OF A PANDEMIC TREATY

The principles outlined in the draft of the pandemic treaty have some legal impacts that must be considered as negotiations continue.

Human rights

A pandemic treaty could profoundly impact human rights, particularly regarding equal access to medical countermeasures and resources, and protection of rights of disadvantaged groups, and promote transparency, accountability and non-discrimination. A human-rights-based approach may offer a comprehensive framework for global health emergencies, close gaps left by the available tools and facilitate global cooperation and coordination. This approach may help to hold governments accountable during a pandemic. However, a pandemic treaty would only be effective if states had the political will to engage in fruitful negotiations and reach a practical agreement. Several scholars discussed the pandemic treaty's potential implications for human rights, including equitable access to medical countermeasures.

According to Pehudoff et al.,⁵³ a pandemic treaty offers a chance to address the issues of equitable access to medical countermeasures, such as vaccines and treatments, which were unfairly distributed during the COVID-19 pandemic. According to the authors, a treaty might enact licensing and technology transfer clauses to create a legal framework for the fair distribution of medical countermeasures. This would guarantee that all nations, regardless of their level of economic development or political influence, have access to the medical resources required to combat pandemics.

Amnesty International, the Global Initiative for Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (GI-ESCR), Human Rights Watch (HRW) and the International Commission of Jurists (ICJ), in a joint public statement, shared their human rights-based concerns regarding the zero draft of the pandemic treaty.⁵⁴ They argued that the zero draft lacks essential points, including predicting human rights obligations for states (for example, regarding improving public health systems, a clear framework for human rights restrictions such as quarantines, and managing the pandemic impacts on marginalised groups of society and health workers). They also emphasise the significance of inserting 'the right to enjoy the benefits of scientific progress' as mentioned in Article 27 of the Universal

⁵³ Katrina Pehudoff, Ellen 't Hoen, Kaitlin Mara, Thirukumaran Balasubramaniam, Frederick Abbott, Brook Baker, et al., 'A pandemic treaty for equitable global access to medical countermeasures: seven recommendations for sharing intellectual property, know-how and technology', *BMJ Global Health* 7 (7) (2022), e009709.

⁵⁴ Amnesty International, the Global Initiative for Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, Human Rights Watch and the International Commission of Jurists, 'Pandemic treaty zero draft misses the mark on human rights: joint public statement' (2023), available at: <https://www.amnesty.org/en/documents/ior40/6478/2023/en/> (27 October 2023).

Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR)⁵⁵ and Article 15 of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR).⁵⁶

The bureau draft (June 2023) and the negotiating draft (October 2023) have weaker language regarding human rights than the zero draft. Some⁵⁷ believe this is backsliding and lacks explicit provisions regarding access to health technologies, transparency and accountability. It also has softer language regarding technology transfer, and some parts regarding ‘gender equality and community engagement’ have been removed.⁵⁸

Some words and options have been added or changed in the two new drafts compared to the zero draft, reflecting apparent divergent views among member states. For example, the phrase ‘as appropriate’ was added to Article 9⁵⁹ in both the bureau and negotiating drafts. Additionally, options present in the bureau draft show differing perspectives. Regarding state duties around sharing information, the June and October 2023 drafts of Article 9 included a qualification about sharing ‘in accordance with national laws’ and ‘as appropriate taking into account the extent of public funding’.

IP law

Intellectual property rights are essential for enhancing innovation and increasing investment in the health sector. Still, they can also make it difficult to access vital drugs and technology in times of public health crisis for LMICs. During the COVID-19 pandemic, many countries, particularly those in the Global South, struggled to access vaccines and other countermeasures because of IP barriers, and the pandemic highlighted the limitations of the current IP regime.

Some solutions for sharing a particular technology with other manufacturers in a health crisis were discussed during the COVID-19 pandemic, including voluntary licensing of vaccines and other countermeasures, compulsory licensing, TRIPS (Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights) waivers,

⁵⁵ Article 27 UDHR: ‘Everyone has the right freely to participate in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits. Everyone has the right to the protection of the moral and material interests resulting from any scientific, literary or artistic production of which he is the author.’

⁵⁶ Article 15 ICESCR: (b) ‘To enjoy the benefits of scientific progress and its applications’.

⁵⁷ BMJ, ‘Covid-19: WHO treaty on future pandemics is being watered down, warn health leaders’, *BMJ* 381 (2023), 1246.

⁵⁸ BMJ, ‘Covid-19’.

⁵⁹ Article 9 bureau draft (June 2023): ‘With a view to promoting greater sharing of knowledge and transparency, each Party, when providing public funding for research and development for pandemic prevention, preparedness, response and recovery of health systems, shall, in accordance with national laws and, as appropriate, taking into account the extent of public funding (a) promote the public dissemination of the results of government-funded research for the development of pandemic-related products, in accessible languages and formats; (b) publish the terms of government-funded research and development agreements for pandemic-related products, as appropriate, including ...’

using initiatives such as COVAX, and patent pools.⁶⁰ A waiver for vaccines and other pandemic-related products is the temporary suspension of IP rights (IPRs), is not limited to patents, and could include trademarks and other IPRs. However, this solution faced many objections during the COVID-19 pandemic, as many governments were afraid of losing the investments of pharmaceutical companies in their countries. Another solution is compulsory licensing, which is limited to patents and is one of the flexibilities of the Convention to Agreement. The government must compensate the patent holder for using their technology in compulsory licensing.⁶¹ Oser suggests that modernising relevant legal provisions can help balance public and private interests, specifically during a health crisis.⁶² Tietze et al. raise the possibility that IP issues could cause a delay in the ‘effective mobilisation of resources’ in the event of a global health emergency.⁶³

The current IP framework, which prioritises preserving IPRs over the interests of the public, can slow down the production and distribution of essential medical supplies and restrict access to reasonably priced medications and vaccinations. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to consider the shortcomings of the existing IP framework and delve into possible solutions to ensure fair and impartial availability of crucial medications and technologies in case of a public health crisis outbreak.⁶⁴ As Matthews posits, having a human rights approach to IPRs during a health crisis is paramount.

The recent case of Humira⁶⁵ regarding excessive pricing of patented pharmaceuticals highlighted the importance of a human-rights approach to IP law and competition law. A new IP protection system included in the pandemic treaty or through other initiatives would help create a more resilient and equitable global health system while addressing the crisis’s immediate concerns. IPRs during the pandemic affect access to vaccines and other pandemic-related products, especially in LMICs, where the price of patented products, inflation,

⁶⁰ Pedro A. Villarreal and Giorgia Renne, ‘Medical countermeasures for pandemic response and intellectual property rights: articulating and enabling community interests under international law’, *International Community Law Review* 24 (3) (2022), 233–56.

⁶¹ Siva Thambisetty, Aisling McMahon, Luke McDonagh, Hyo Yoon Kang and Graham Duffield, ‘The TRIPS intellectual property waiver proposal: creating the right incentives in patent law and politics to end the COVID-19 pandemic’, LSE Legal Studies Working Paper No. 06/2021 (2021), available at: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3851737 (27 October 2023).

⁶² Andreas Oser, ‘The COVID-19 pandemic: stress test for intellectual property and pharmaceutical laws’, *GRUR International* 70 (9) (2021), 846–54.

⁶³ Frank Tietze, Pratheeba Vimalnath, Leonidas Aristodemou and Jenny Molloy, ‘Crisis-critical intellectual property: findings from the COVID-19 pandemic’, *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management* 69 (5) (2020), 2039–56.

⁶⁴ For a different perspective, see Reto Hilty, Pedro Henrique D. Batista, Suelen Carls, Daria Kim, Matthias Lamping and Peter R. Slowinski, ‘COVID-19 and the role of intellectual property: position statement of the Max Planck Institute for Innovation and Competition of 7 May 2021’, Max Planck Institute for Innovation & Competition Research Paper No. 21-13, available at: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3841549 (27 October 2023); Felix Addor, ‘How (not) to sleepwalk into the next pandemic!’, *International Review of Intellectual Property and Competition Law* 54 (2023), 821–5.

⁶⁵ Rosalind Turkie, ‘AbbVie overcharged the Dutch health care system by as much as €1.2 billion for Humira’, Pharmaceutical Accountability Foundation, available at: <https://www.pharmaceuticalaccountability.org/2023/02/21/abbvie-overcharged-the-dutch-health-care-system-by-as-much-as-e1-2-billion-for-humira> (20 September 2023).

low salaries and other social and economic factors are significant. The zero draft, bureau draft (June 2023) and negotiating draft (October 2023) differ regarding the IP provisions for pandemic-related products. Article 7 of the zero draft (see Appendix) outlines the obligations of the parties using phrases such as ‘cooperate’, ‘provide’, ‘monitor’ and ‘review’. Article 11 of the June 2023 draft (see Appendix) describes the conduct of member states in more precise and explicit terms, such as ‘coordinate’, ‘collaborate’, ‘facilitate’, ‘incentivise’ and ‘ensure’.

Article 11 (June 2023) offers two options with different levels of commitment and obligation for the parties regarding IP waivers. Option A is more binding, while Option B is more flexible and voluntary. Article 7 (zero draft) has no alternative options, only a set of provisions similar to Option A of Article 11 regarding commitment and obligation. Article 11 of the negotiating draft (October 2023) follows the same format. Hence, the legal language of the zero draft and negotiating draft are more binding (see Appendix).

Article 11 (June 2023) also introduces specific mechanisms and initiatives for ‘technology transfer’, such as ‘technology transfer hubs’, ‘product development partnerships’ and ‘developing a database for pandemic-related products’. These elements are not mentioned in Article 7 of the zero draft. Both articles acknowledge the need for ‘increased manufacturing capacity that is geographically and strategically distributed’, especially in developing countries. They propose various mechanisms to ‘facilitate technology transfer’, including ‘licensing agreements, waivers of intellectual property rights and royalties, and coordination with relevant international organisations’.

Article 11 of the October 2023 negotiating draft seeks to balance these options (mentioned in the June 2023 draft) by incorporating binding elements on strengthening mechanisms from Option 11.A, while allowing flexibility based on mutually agreed terms as per Option 11.B. It focuses on pandemics while including provisions on TRIPS flexibilities and IP waivers (see Appendix).

Finding an effective solution in the pandemic treaty to combat the inequities in the following health crises could make it easier to produce and distribute necessary medical supplies, including vaccines, personal protective equipment and diagnostic tests, while giving IP owners a fair return on their investment.

Tort law

A ‘global compensation mechanism for vaccine injuries’ is a legal framework that provides compensation for injuries caused by vaccines. COVID-19 vaccines were developed and produced through a rather unusual fast-track process that usually takes years of research, development, trial, approval and manufacturing. Although the vaccines were effective and saved millions of lives globally, the need for a compensation mechanism for vaccine-related injuries is relevant in an

international pandemic treaty. The no-fault compensation programme is an alternative to the traditional tort law compensation framework that allows individuals to receive compensation without proving negligence and fault of vaccine producers through litigation. This framework for potential side-effects helps to increase equity and should be part of the steps taken to better prepare for the next crisis.

Fewer than 30 jurisdictions worldwide have a no-fault compensation programme,⁶⁶ including the National Vaccine Injury Compensation Program (VICP)⁶⁷ in the US. In the EU, sixteen countries have this programme.⁶⁸ The COVAX No-Fault Compensation Program⁶⁹ was one of the steps taken internationally. A global compensation framework requires a large amount of funding and will depend on the resources of WHO members.

Article 10 of the pandemic treaty bureau draft (June 2023) proposed a ‘vaccine injury compensation scheme’. This Article stated:

The Parties shall establish, no later than XX, regional or international vaccine injury compensation scheme(s) based on existing relevant models. These scheme(s) shall be transparent and complement any liability protections and/or other liability risk management mechanisms for injuries caused by the use and/or administration of vaccines developed for pandemics [...] Each Party shall publicly disclose information on any global, regional, or country-level liability frameworks and vaccine compensation scheme that applies to the production, distribution, administration, or use of pandemic-related products in its jurisdiction, in accordance with national laws.

In the same vein, Article 15 of the negotiating draft (October 2023) requires that parties develop national strategies for managing liability risks from novel pandemic vaccines, including compensation mechanisms, and tasks the Conference of Parties with establishing no-fault vaccine injury compensation mechanisms within two years to promote access to remedies and vaccine acceptance. Parties shall also aim to limit indemnity clauses in vaccine supply contracts.

⁶⁶ For a list of these countries and a review of each jurisdiction programme, see Stefano D’Errico, Martina Zanon, Monica Concato, Michela Peruch, Matteo Scopetti, Paola Frati and Vittorio Fineschi, “‘First do no harm’: no-fault compensation program for COVID-19 vaccines as feasibility and wisdom of a policy instrument to mitigate vaccine hesitancy”, *Vaccines* 9 (10) (2021), 1116.

⁶⁷ National Vaccine Injury Compensation Program, available at: <https://www.hrsa.gov/vaccine-compensation/index.html> (20 September 2023).

⁶⁸ Ireland does not have such a mechanism yet: Jessica Doyle and Eoin McLoughlin, ‘Vaccine injury compensation programmes: an overview’, Oireachtas Library & Research Service, available at: https://data.oireachtas.ie/ie/oireachtas/libraryResearch/2021/2021-04-20_1-rs-note-vaccine-injury-compensation-programmes-an-overview_en.pdf (31 May 2023); Mary-Elizabeth Tumelty, Mary Donnelly, Anne-Maree Farrell and Clayton Ó Néill, ‘COVID-19 vaccination and legal preparedness: lessons from Ireland’, *European Journal of Health Law* 29 (2) (2022), 240–59.

⁶⁹ WHO, ‘No-fault compensation programme for COVID-19 vaccines is a world first’, available at: <https://www.who.int/news/item/22-02-2021-no-fault-compensation-programme-for-COVID-19-vaccines-is-a-world-first> (20 September 2023).

The pandemic treaty (zero draft) stressed the need for a ‘global compensation mechanism’. However, the bureau draft (June 2023) and the negotiating draft (October 2023) have weakened this aspect and shifted the focus to national frameworks. This may reflect the challenge of securing funding for such a scheme across countries.

Global health law

Global health law is a relatively new branch encompassing several international treaties, agreements, guidelines, regulations, norms, principles and standards. It is a multidisciplinary field related to public health, human rights, international law, environmental law, IP law, medical law and ethics.⁷⁰ Global health law changed dramatically after the emergence of COVID-19 as the shortcomings of global solidarity and the current IHR were highlighted. Some aspects of the pandemic treaty will impact global health law.

Common but Differentiated Responsibilities (CBDR)⁷¹ is a guiding principle in international climate change law,⁷² which was recently discussed as a principle in global health law. This principle acknowledges the responsibility of all states for a health crisis, but at different levels. It means countries with more capacities and resources have a higher responsibility regarding the global crisis and could help and support LMICs. According to the previous version of the pandemic treaty’s draft (the zero draft), ‘States that hold more resources relevant to pandemics, including pandemic-related products and manufacturing capacity, should bear a commensurate degree of differentiated responsibility concerning a global pandemic.’ In the bureau draft (June 2023), this Article changed dramatically, and, as Habibi and Wenham⁷³ argue, there seems to be massive opposition to it from the developed countries. In the bureau draft, governments have three options available, including a third option of not including the principle, and the article’s tone has changed (see the Appendix).

⁷⁰ See Lawrence O. Gostin and Allyn L. Taylor, ‘Global health law: a definition and grand challenges’, *Public Health Ethics* 1 (1) (2008), 53–63; Michel Bélanger, *Global health law: an introduction* (Cambridge, 2011); Lawrence O. Gostin and Benjamin Mason Meier, ‘Introducing global health law’, *Journal of Law, Medicine & Ethics* 47 (4) (2019), 788–93.

⁷¹ Chenguang Wang and Yi Zhang, ‘Common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities as a guiding principle in international health law in times of pandemics’, in Maarten den Heijer and Harmen van der Wilt (eds), *Netherlands yearbook of international law 2020: global solidarity and common but differentiated responsibilities* (The Hague, 2022), 257–82.

⁷² United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, 1992. Article 3.1: ‘The parties should protect the climate system for the benefit of present and future generations of humankind, on the basis of equity and in accordance with their common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities. Accordingly, the developed country Parties should take the lead in combating climate change and the adverse effects thereof.’ Available at: <https://unfccc.int/resource/docs/convkp/conveng.pdf> (20 September 2023).

⁷³ Roojin Habibi and Clare Wenham, ‘The world is running out of time to negotiate a global pandemic treaty’, available at: <https://www.theglobeandmail.com/opinion/article-the-world-is-running-out-of-time-to-negotiate-a-global-pandemic-treaty> (20 September 2023).

According to Article 3 of the negotiating draft (October 2023), ‘Recognition of different levels of capacity’ is one of the general principles and approaches in the treaty. In this article, ‘Countries have varying levels of pandemic prevention, preparedness and response capacities which presents a common danger, such that support to countries with capacity needs is required, within means and resources available.’ Pathogen access and benefit-sharing (ABS) is a critical aspect of global health and a challenging part of the pandemic treaty’s negotiations. ABS refers to the equitable sharing of benefits from using genetic resources (including pathogens). Like the CBDR, this is an international environmental law principle first mentioned in the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the Nagoya Protocol on Genetic Resources. Using this framework during a pandemic can help share data, knowledge and pathogens. Pathogens are essential factors in developing vaccines, treatments and diagnostics. Some believe it is an ineffective system,⁷⁴ and some in the pharmaceutical industry, mostly because of IP rights and innovation claims, are against the pathogen ABS.⁷⁵

Competition law and public procurement

The COVID-19 pandemic has brought about new difficulties in enforcing competition law, resulting in the use of a temporary framework in the competition laws of the EU and many other jurisdictions that permits the inclusion of public or non-economic interests.⁷⁶ As Kozak⁷⁷ argued, public interest objectives in competition law are needed during a pandemic, when undertakings may prioritise profits at the expense of social welfare.

The pandemic treaty might have a few impacts on competition law enforcement. Many argue that the flexibility of competition rules reflects pandemic concerns better, ensuring the appropriate weighting of public interest objectives. Some authors discussed the relationship between solidarity and competition law.⁷⁸ This is also important in global health and global health crises. Guy examines whether and how competition law can and should address economic inequities in healthcare.⁷⁹

⁷⁴ Abbie-Rose Hampton, Mark Eccleston-Turner, Michelle Rourke and Stephanie Switzer, ‘Equity in the pandemic treaty: access and benefit-sharing as a policy device or a rhetorical device?’, *Journal of Law, Medicine & Ethics* 51 (1) (2023), 217–20.

⁷⁵ IFMPA, ‘WHO Intergovernmental Negotiating Body (INB) intercessional briefing on access and benefit sharing’, available at: <https://www.ifpma.org/news/who-intergovernmental-negotiating-body-inb-intercessional-briefing-on-access-and-benefit-sharing> (2 June 2023).

⁷⁶ See Frederick M. Abbott, ‘Using competition law to promote access to health technologies: a supplement to the Guidebook for low- and middle-income countries’ (New York, 2022).

⁷⁷ Malgorza Kozak, ‘Competition law and the COVID-19 pandemic – towards more room for public interest objectives?’, *Utrecht Law Review* 17 (3) (2021), 118–29.

⁷⁸ See Nina Boeger, ‘Solidarity and EC competition law’, *European Law Review* 32 (2007), 319–40; Malcolm Ross, ‘Promoting solidarity: from public services to a European model of competition’, *Common Market Law Review* 44 (2007), 1057–80.

⁷⁹ Mary Guy, ‘Competition law, inequalities and healthcare: insights from EU and national frameworks’, in Jan Broulik and Katalin Cseres (eds), *Competition law and economic inequality* (London, 2022).

During the pandemic, one of the crisis measures in the EU and the rest of the world was to relax some parts of competition law enforcement in the health sector.⁸⁰ Cooperation and collaboration between rivals, prohibited in normal enforcement of competition law, is encouraged in a crisis. In the pandemic treaty, collaboration and cooperation between companies, sharing information, joint research and development and joint procurement, would raise competition law concerns.

The crisis also impacted state aid rules, and the pandemic treaty's provisions on state aid, state funding and subsidies in the health sector will affect national regulations regarding state aid. Abuse of dominance by pharmaceutical companies and vaccine producers, such as excessive pricing⁸¹ of pandemic-related products, is another critical issue that arose during the pandemic and is mentioned in the pandemic treaty's draft.

The zero draft had a provision regarding public funding and research and development information; it mentioned that 'manufacturers who receive public funding for the production of pandemic-related products have this responsibility to disclose prices and contractual terms for public procurement in times of pandemic', which would have had substantial competition law impact and would increase accountability and transparency in the public procurement of pandemic-related products. This provision was deleted in the bureau draft (June 2023) and the negotiating draft (October 2023), which is a step backwards for pandemic transparency and increasing equity.

THE OBSTACLES TO THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PANDEMIC TREATY

There are a number of potential obstacles to the pandemic treaty's implementation. Previous experiences of the global community in implementing international legal documents such as IHR were unsuccessful in increasing global health solidarity. Labonté et al.⁸² mention that the IHR failed to perform well during the COVID-19 pandemic and was ineffective in compelling states to take

⁸⁰ The European Commission followed a flexible approach in competition law enforcement during the COVID-19 pandemic. See, for example, 'Comfort letter: coordination in the pharmaceutical industry to increase production and to improve supply of urgently needed critical hospital medicines to treat COVID-19 patients', Brussels, 8 April 2020, available at: https://www.skadden.com/-/media/files/publications/2020/11/green-competition/fn5_medicines_for_europe_comfort_letter.pdf?la=en (27 October 2023); 'Comfort letter: cooperation at a matchmaking event – towards COVID-19 vaccines upscale production', Brussels, 25 March 2021, available at: https://competition-policy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-09/comfort_letter_coronavirus_matchmaking_event_25032021.pdf (27 October 2023).

⁸¹ Behrang Kianzad, 'Excessive pricing during COVID-19 crisis in EU – an empirical inquiry', *Concurrences* (1) (2021), available at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3715392> (20 September 2023).

⁸² Ronald Labonté, Mary Wiktorowicz, Corinne Packer, Arne Ruckert, Kumanan Wilson and Sam Halabi, 'A pandemic treaty, revised international health regulations, or both?', *Globalization and Health* 17 (128) (2021).

action. The authors contend that a pandemic treaty could complement the IHR and offer a more holistic approach to dealing with global health crises, with clauses on access to pandemic-related products, surveillance and reporting. A pandemic treaty without legal consequences and penalties for non-compliance would be a weak and ineffective instrument. Such an international instrument would fail to foster global health solidarity and prevent future pandemics. As we saw in the previous sections, the latest drafts of the treaty contain vague legal terms that undermine its binding force and effectiveness.

The legal basis of the treaty is a subject of debate, with options including ‘conventions or agreements’ under Article 19 of the WHO constitution,⁸³ ‘regulations’ under Article 21⁸⁴ or ‘recommendations’ under Article 23.⁸⁵

The legal language of the pandemic treaty is another potential challenge. If the treaty uses vocabulary that merely encourages or suggests that parties take specific actions rather than mandating them, it may resemble non-binding documents. Phrases such as ‘parties are encouraged to’, ‘they should’, ‘they endeavour’, ‘they should promote’ and ‘as appropriate’⁸⁶ may not be strong enough to ensure compliance. To be more effective, the treaty may need more robust legal language that requires parties to take specific steps.

Political willingness in the negotiations of the pandemic treaty up to this point has been challenging. Stronger cooperation and information sharing between countries is necessary during a pandemic, and it is expected that the pandemic treaty could enhance such arrangements. This tension between Global North and Global South on aspects of the pandemic treaty, such as IP debates and innovation versus access and equity arguments, technology⁸⁷ and the national ratification and adoption process of the treaty in each country, makes it challenging to be effective.

⁸³ WHO Constitution Article 19: ‘The Health Assembly shall have authority to adopt conventions or agreements with respect to any matter within the competence of the Organization. A two-thirds vote of the Health Assembly shall be required for the adoption of such conventions or agreements, which shall come into force for each Member when accepted by it in accordance with its constitutional processes.’

⁸⁴ WHO Constitution Article 21: ‘The Health Assembly shall have authority to adopt regulations concerning: (a) sanitary and quarantine requirements and other procedures designed to prevent the international spread of disease; (b) nomenclatures with respect to diseases, causes of death and public health practices; (c) standards with respect to diagnostic procedures for international use; (d) standards with respect to the safety, purity and potency of biological, pharmaceutical and similar products moving in international commerce; (e) advertising and labelling of biological, pharmaceutical and similar products moving in international commerce.’

⁸⁵ WHO Constitution Article 23: ‘The Health Assembly shall have authority to make recommendations to Members with respect to any matter within the competence of the Organization.’

⁸⁶ In the recent Draft (June 2023), ‘as appropriate’ was used 47 times. See Mariana Lenharo, ‘Global plan for dealing with next pandemic just got weaker, critics say’, *Nature News* (2023), available at: <https://www.nature.com/articles/d41586-023-01805-4> (2 June 2023).

⁸⁷ For some of these tensions, see, for example, Kerry Cullinan, ‘Sharp disagreement over intellectual property at WHO pandemic treaty consultation’, *Health Policy Watch*, 8 October 2022, available at: <https://health-policy-watch.news/sharp-disagreement-over-intellectual-property-at-who-pandemic-treaty-consultation/> (26 September 2023).

CONCLUSION

As this paper has suggested, while building a global health solidarity framework to tackle future pandemics through a pandemic treaty is challenging, it can potentially establish a practical framework. The COVID-19 experience proved that pandemic inequities, lack of cooperation, human rights violations, vaccine nationalism, excessive pricing of pandemic-related products, IP barriers, vaccine hoarding and pandemic profiteering could lead to a failure in reaching global solidarity. The paper analysed the arguments for and against a pandemic treaty and reflected on the concerns over the effectiveness of the current draft of the treaty.

In terms of building global health solidarity in a permacrisis, the paper investigated the legal impacts of the treaty on human rights, competition law and public procurement, IP law, tort law and global health law. The pandemic treaty aims to offer an international legal framework for creating a more equitable global health system. It emphasises solidarity, equity in pandemic-related product access, transparency, accountability and collaboration. However, the current draft of the treaty (October 2023) has limitations. Many options, weak legal language, lack of appropriate sanctions, ambiguity in IP rights waivers and flexibilities, shortcomings in designing a global compensation mechanism, lack of adequate provisions regarding public funding in producing pandemic-related products and lack of transparency are some of the legal concerns regarding the treaty.

APPENDIX

Article 7. Zero draft: Access to technology: promoting sustainable and equitably distributed production and transfer of technology and know-how

‘1. The Parties recognize that inequitable access to pandemic-related products (including but not limited to vaccines, therapeutics and diagnostics) should be addressed by increased manufacturing capacity that is more equitably, geographically and strategically distributed. 2. The Parties, working through the Governing Body for the WHO CA+, shall strengthen existing and develop innovative multilateral mechanisms that promote and incentivize relevant transfer of technology and know-how for production of pandemic-related products, on mutually agreed terms, to capable manufacturers, particularly in developing countries. 3. During inter-pandemic times, all Parties commit to establish these mechanisms and shall: (a) coordinate, collaborate, facilitate and incentivize manufacturers of pandemic-related products to transfer relevant technology and know-how to capable manufacturer(s) (as defined below) on mutually agreed terms, including through technology transfer hubs and product development partnerships, and to address the needs to develop new

pandemic-related products in a short time frame; (b) strengthen coordination, with relevant international organizations, including United Nations agencies, on issues related to public health, intellectual property and trade, including timely matching of supply to demand and mapping manufacturing capacities and demand; (c) encourage entities, including manufacturers within their respective jurisdictions, that conduct research and development of pre-pandemic and pandemic-related products, in particular those that receive significant public financing for that purpose, to grant, on mutually agreed terms, licences to capable manufacturers, notably from developing countries, to use their intellectual property and other protected substances, products, technology, know-how, information and knowledge used in the process of pandemic response product research, development and production, in particular for pre-pandemic and pandemic-related products; and (d) collaborate to ensure equitable and affordable access to health technologies that promote the strengthening of national health systems and mitigate social inequalities. 4. In the event of a pandemic, the Parties: (a) will take appropriate measures to support time-bound waivers of intellectual property rights that can accelerate or scale up manufacturing of pandemic-related products during a pandemic, to the extent necessary to increase the availability and adequacy of affordable pandemic-related products; (b) will apply the full use of the flexibilities provided in the TRIPS Agreement, including those recognized in the Doha Declaration on the TRIPS Agreement and Public Health of 2001 and in Articles 27, 30 (including the research exception and “Bolar” provision), 31 and 31bis of the TRIPS Agreement; (c) shall encourage all holders of patents related to the production of pandemic-related products to waive, or manage as appropriate, payment of royalties by developing country manufacturers on the use, during the pandemic, of their technology for production of pandemic-related products, and shall require, as appropriate, those that have received public financing for the development of pandemic-related products to do so; and (d) shall encourage all research and development institutes, including manufacturers, in particular those receiving significant public financing, to waive, or manage as appropriate, royalties on the continued use of their technology for production of pandemic-related products. 5. For purposes of this Article, “capable manufacturer” refers to an entity that operates in a manner that is consistent with national and international guidelines and regulations, including biosafety and biosecurity standards.’

Article 11. Bureau draft (June 2023): Co-development and transfer of technology and know-how

‘Two options are presented for Article 11. Option 11.A1. The Parties recognize that inequitable access to pandemic-related products (including but not limited

to vaccines, therapeutics and diagnostics) should be addressed by increased manufacturing capacity that is more equitably, geographically and strategically distributed. 2. The Parties, working through the Conference of the Parties, shall strengthen existing and develop innovative multilateral mechanisms, including through the pooling of knowledge, intellectual property and data, that promote the relevant transfer of technology and know-how for the production of pandemic-related products, on mutually agreed terms as appropriate, to manufacturers, particularly in developing countries. 3. The Parties shall ensure that manufacturers of pandemic-related products are strategically and geographically distributed in order to maximize access to complete pandemic-related products for countries in which developing manufacturing capacity is not feasible. 4. During inter-pandemic periods, all Parties commit to establishing these mechanisms and shall: (a) coordinate, collaborate, facilitate and incentivize the manufacturers of pandemic-related products to transfer the relevant technology and know-how to manufacturer(s) (as defined below) on mutually agreed terms as appropriate, including through technology transfer hubs and product development partnerships, and to address the need to develop new pandemic-related products in a short time frame; (b) strengthen coordination, with relevant international organizations, including United Nations agencies, on issues related to public health, intellectual property and trade, including the timely matching of supply to demand and mapping manufacturing capacities and demand; (c) encourage entities, including manufacturers within their respective jurisdictions, that conduct research and development of pre-pandemic and pandemic-related products, in particular those that receive significant public financing for that purpose, to grant, on mutually agreed terms as appropriate, licences to manufacturers, notably from developing countries, to use their intellectual property and other protected substances, products, technology, know-how, information and knowledge used in the process of pandemic response product research, development and production, in particular for pre-pandemic and pandemic-related products; (d) collaborate to ensure equitable and affordable access to health technologies that promote the strengthening of national health systems and mitigate social inequalities; and (e) develop a database that provides the details of pandemic-related products for all known pandemic potential diseases, including the technological specifications and manufacturing process documents for each product ...; (c) encourage all holders of patents related to the production of pandemic-related products to waive or manage, as appropriate, the payment of royalties by developing country manufacturers on the use, during the pandemic, of their technology for the production of pandemic-related products, and shall require, as appropriate, those that have received public financing for the development of pandemic-related products to do so; and (d) encourage all research and development institutes, including manufacturers, in particular those receiving significant public financing, to

waive or manage, as appropriate, royalties on the continued use of their technology for production of pandemic-related products ...’

Article 11. Negotiating draft (October 2023): Transfer of technology and know-how

1. The Parties, within a set time frame, working through the Conference of the Parties, shall strengthen existing, and develop innovative, multilateral mechanisms, including through the pooling of knowledge, intellectual property and data, that promote the relevant transfer of technology and know-how for the production of pandemic-related products, on mutually agreed terms as appropriate, to manufacturers, particularly in developing countries.
2. The Parties shall: (a) coordinate with, collaborate with, facilitate and incentivize the manufacturers of pandemic related products to transfer the relevant technology and know-how to manufacturer(s) on mutually agreed terms as appropriate, including through technology transfer hubs and product development partnerships, and to address the need to develop new pandemic-related products in a short time frame; (b) make available non-exclusive licensing of government-owned technologies on mutually agreed terms as appropriate, for the development and manufacturing of pandemic-related products, and publish the terms of these licenses; (c) make use of the flexibilities provided in the Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS Agreement), including those recognized in the Doha Declaration on the TRIPS Agreement and Public Health of 2001 and in Articles 27, 30 (including the research exception and the ‘Bolar’ provision), 31 and 31bis of the TRIPS Agreement, and fully respect the use thereof by others; (d) collaborate to ensure equitable and affordable access to health technologies that promote the strengthening of national health systems and mitigate social inequalities; (e) develop a database that provides the details of pandemic-related products for all known pandemic potential diseases, including the technological specifications and manufacturing process documents for each product; and (f) provide, within their capabilities, resources to support capacity-building for the development and transfer of relevant technology, skills and know-how, and to facilitate access to other sources of support.
3. During pandemics, each Party shall, in addition to the undertakings in paragraph 2 of this Article: (a) commit to agree upon, within the framework of relevant institutions, time-bound waivers of intellectual property rights to accelerate or scale up the manufacturing of pandemic-related products during a pandemic, to the extent necessary to increase the

availability and adequacy of affordable pandemic-related products; (b) encourage all holders of patents related to the production of pandemic-related products to waive or manage, as appropriate, for a limited duration, the payment of royalties by developing country manufacturers on the use, during the pandemic, of their technology for the production of pandemic-related products, and shall require, as appropriate, those that have received public financing for the development of pandemic-related products to do so; and (c) encourage manufacturers within its jurisdiction to share undisclosed information, as defined in Article 39.2 of the TRIPS Agreement, with qualified third-party manufacturers where such information prevents or hinders urgent manufacture by such qualified third parties of a pharmaceutical product that is necessary to respond to the pandemic.

4. The Parties shall, with a view to effective pandemic response, when engaged in bilateral or regional trade or investment negotiations, take steps so that negotiated provisions do not interfere with the full use of the flexibilities provided in the TRIPS Agreement, including those recognized in the Doha Declaration on the TRIPS Agreement and Public Health.

Article 3-7 Bureau draft (June 2023)

Three options are presented for principle 7: Option 7. A: Common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities in pandemic prevention, preparedness, response and recovery of health systems – Governments have a responsibility for the health of their people, which can be fulfilled only by the provision of adequate health and social measures. Given the unequal development in different countries in the promotion of health and control of diseases, especially communicable disease is a common danger, Parties that hold more capacities and resources relevant to pandemics should bear a commensurate degree of differentiated responsibility regarding global pandemic prevention, preparedness, response and recovery. Option 7. B: Common responsibilities and different capabilities in pandemic prevention, preparedness, response and recovery of health systems – Governments have a responsibility for the health of their peoples, which can be fulfilled only by the provision of adequate health and social measures. Option 7. C: not to include as a principle.

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